
Synthesis Review: Impacts of Climate Change on Agriculture, Human Health, and Food Security and Safety.

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ABSTRACT

Current research on the complex effects of climate change on agriculture, food security, and human health is summarized in this review. It examines how climate change may affect agricultural productivity both negatively and positively. It discusses the difficulties brought on by a rise in pests, a shortage of water, and degraded soil, as well as any potential advantages like CO₂ fertilization and longer growing seasons. The analysis goes into additional detail about the consequences for food security, highlighting the threats that changing climate conditions have to food safety and availability. It draws attention to growing worries about pesticide residues, mycotoxin contamination in crops, and foodborne diseases. The review also discusses the growing risk of vector-borne illnesses impacting human health as a result of changes in disease vectors' geographic ranges brought on by climate change. In order to fully comprehend and address these intricate difficulties, more study is clearly required, as the document's conclusion calls for integrated mitigation and adaptation methods. The review provides a resource for comprehending how agricultural practices, food safety, and public health are impacted by climate change.

Keywords: Climate Change, Environmental Changes, Food Security, Food Safety, Agricultural Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

While global warming has serious consequences for agriculture, food security, and human health, it is also crucial to recognize that there may be some benefits, albeit limited and context-dependent. As reported by NOAA in 2020 (NOAA Climate.gov, 2020), several locations may have milder winters, potentially leading to lower fatality rates linked with cold waves. Furthermore, in some places, longer growing seasons and higher CO₂ levels may boost crop productivity. However, it is critical to note that the larger and more severe repercussions of global warming, such as enhanced heat waves, damaged ecosystems, and a rise in the frequency of extreme weather events, typically outweigh these potential benefits. This, in turn, directly jeopardizes food security by impacting food availability, accessibility, and stability, as regions face the risk of reduced crop yields and loss of arable land.

Furthermore, food safety is compromised due to the escalation of pesticide residues, the proliferation of foodborne pathogens, and the elevated risk of mycotoxin contamination in crops.

The problem is negotiating these complicated and multifaceted repercussions while attempting to mitigate the negative outcomes, while cautiously examining any potential benefits that global warming might offer.

Positive Impacts on Agriculture

The following are some important findings that may be made from some studies and publications (Kim & UN.ESCAP, 2012; NASA, 2020; NOAA Climate.gov, 2020; Wreford et al., 2010) about the difficulties and possible advantages that climate change effects may present for agriculture.

- Temperature rise and elevated CO₂: Elevated CO₂ and rising temperatures have the ability to accelerate the development of some crops. Scientists call this process "CO₂ fertilization." According to some studies, under such circumstances, some crops, like rice, wheat, and barley, might grow and yield more.

- Longer growth seasons: warmer weather in some areas may result in longer growth seasons. Longer growing seasons and maybe larger harvests annually could result from this, especially in regions where past winter weather has restricted agricultural activity.

- Changes in possible cropping locations: as a result of climate change, formerly unfeasible agricultural locations may now be suitable due to milder temperatures. Certain crops may now be able to be grown in areas where they were previously unsuitable for cultivation, thanks to this change.

- Adaptation and resilience: the significance of agricultural adaptation measures entails creating crop types resistant to drought, enhancing irrigation effectiveness, and implementing climate-smart farming techniques. These tactics can maximize any possible advantages of climate change while assisting in reducing its negative effects.

- Possibility of diversification: agricultural diversification may be encouraged by changing climatic circumstances. It may be necessary for farmers to adjust by planting a greater range of crops, some of which may be better adapted to the altered environmental circumstances.

- Risks and challenges: all studies point out a number of important risks in addition to some possible advantages. These include the potential for agricultural destruction caused by an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events such as droughts and floods, changes in pest and disease patterns that impact crop health, and difficulties relating to water supply.

- Economic and policy adaptations: in order to help agriculture adapt to climate change, the need for economic and policy adaptations is considered paramount. This involves funding for scientific and

technological advancements, encouragement of environmentally friendly agricultural methods, and legislation aimed at lowering greenhouse gas emissions from the sector of agriculture.

- Regional variability: there will be substantial regional differences in how climate change affects agriculture. While there may be possible benefits in some areas, there may be primarily negative effects in others.

It seems obvious, though, that this "Elevated CO₂" advantage has a drawback: a warmer planet would also encourage the growth of weeds, numerous invasive plant species, and insect pests. Affected agricultural areas that require irrigation and are drier will have less water available. The negative effects of heat stress and drought will eventually probably outweigh the benefits of more carbon dioxide for crops.

Negative Impacts on Agriculture

Some of the obstacles and constraints related to the effects of climate change on agriculture are also well-reported. The following are the main aspects of the difficulties and constraints related to the effects of climate change on agriculture:

- Growth of weeds and pests: as a result of their competition with crops for resources, invasive plant species, and weeds are more likely to proliferate in warmer climates. Similar to this, a lot of insect pests do better in warmer climates, which could result in more serious infestations and crop damage.

- Water scarcity: in already arid agricultural regions, rising temperatures and changed precipitation patterns might make the situation worse. For areas where crop production depends on irrigation, this is a serious worry. A shortage of water not only lowers crop yields but also drives up the cost of agricultural output by necessitating the use of more expensive but more effective irrigation technology.

- Heat stress and drought: under some circumstances, elevated CO₂ levels can promote plant development, but these advantages are probably offset by the detrimental effects of heat stress and drought. Since

most crops are vulnerable to high temperatures, particularly during crucial growth stages like flowering and seed setting, high temperatures might result in lower agricultural yields.

- Decreasing benefits of CO₂ fertilization: over time, the initial advantages of CO₂ fertilization may wear off. The effect could be lessened if plants adapt to increased CO₂ levels. Furthermore, the advantages of CO₂ depend on the availability of other resources, such as fertilizers and water, which may be scarce as a result of climate change.

- Soil degradation: loss of nutrients, soil erosion, and deterioration of soil structure can all be made worse by climate change. This deterioration may lessen the soil's capacity to sustain crop growth, hence reducing the advantages of elevated CO₂.

- Adaptation limits: although adaptation techniques can lessen certain adverse effects, their efficacy has a limit. For example, creating crop types resistant to heat is a partial solution to the overall effects of temperature rise and changes in precipitation patterns.

- Uneven geographic impact: there will be significant regional variations in how climate change affects agriculture. Global food security and market dynamics may be impacted by agricultural productivity gains in some areas that are later countered by negative effects in other regions.

Human Health

Through a variety of mechanisms, climate change can exacerbate existing health problems or create new public health challenges (Crimmins et al., 2016).

Does global warming increase the risk of epidemic infectious diseases? This may be true for some infectious disorders: one growing issue for human health is that we do not completely understand how climate change is affecting the geographic ranges of vector-borne diseases, which are illnesses caused by bacteria, viruses, and parasites that are spread to humans through an intermediary host organism. Lyme disease, West Nile virus, Malaria, emerging mosquito-

borne Zika virus, human parasites, etc. Nevertheless, a number of factors, including climate change, can accelerate the spread of infectious diseases. The lifecycles of diseases and the animals that transport and spread them are impacted by changes in land use and land cover in addition to global warming: changes in land use and land cover, often a consequence of both climate change and human activity, can alter the interaction between humans and potential disease vectors. Deforestation, urbanization, and agricultural expansion can bring humans into closer contact with vectors, thereby increasing the risk of disease transmission. But, more research is needed to further establish the links between climate, infectious illnesses, and various other elements in order to better predict the risks of infectious disease epidemics in a changing climate (Parham et al., 2015). Even so, given the potential for increased spread of infectious diseases due to climate change, public health systems need to be prepared. This involves surveillance, early warning systems, public education on disease prevention, and strategies to control and manage disease outbreaks.

Impact on Food Security

Climate change, according to the USDA, is likely to disrupt global food security through, among other things, production disruptions that lead to local supply constraints and price hikes, interrupted transit channels, and decreased food safety (USDA, 2015).

Without concerted efforts to address the impacts of climate change on agriculture, food supply and security are at risk. This is particularly concerning given the expected increase in global population and the subsequent rise in food demand over the next 30 years. At the same time, the way food is frequently manufactured nowadays contributes significantly to the problem. According to recent estimates, the global food system is responsible for roughly one-third of greenhouse gas emissions, second only to the energy sector; it is the leading source of methane and biodiversity loss (FAO, 2015).

Water-stressed areas, pests and illnesses, decreased fertility, availability, and degradation of soil resources

are all major barriers to boosting food output and quality (Tilman et al., 2011). Climate change adds complexity to an already complicated agro-ecological system. It is now necessary to prioritize creating adaptation and mitigation plans and choices over impact assessment from the standpoint of food security (Chakraborty & Newton, 2011). Food supply and food security will be severely compromised in the next 30 years if little or no action is made to address climate change and the food system's sensitivity to climate change.

Impact on Food Safety

Specifically addressing food safety concerns, the common perspective of how climate change affects food safety effectively conveys the intricacies and difficulties that the food business faces, especially when it comes to chemical and microbiological contamination.

The European Food Safety Agency in its article on "Emerging Risks in 2021" (Gkrintzali et al., 2023) warns about the possibility of new hazards arising from reduced usage of fertilizers and pesticides: the farm-to-fork approach aims to cut the total amount of chemical pesticides used by 50% by 2030. In order to meet this goal, farmers must ensure food security and environmental safety while also addressing a growing number of demands and limitations, including the rising demand for food, feed, and non-food outlet production; the rise in new pests and diseases brought on by the effects of climate change; and the escalating standards for the safety and quality of agricultural products.

In our line of work, as managers overseeing Quality Control and Food Safety, the evaluation by Miguel Machado Cruz is quite pertinent (Cruz, 2023). To emphasize a few important points:

- Chemical contaminants, with higher pesticide residues as a result of changing insect dynamics, climate change may require pesticides to be used more frequently. This may lead to increased pesticide residue levels in crops, which may have an impact on the safety and health of consumers.

- Crop mycotoxins, that may be the consequence are caused by temperature and humidity fluctuations, which create an environment that is conducive to the growth of mold. Food items, like processed tomato products, may become contaminated and lose their quality and becoming a non-safe food product (Perrone et al., 2020).

- Microbiological contaminants with modified water quality providing a way to microbiological pollutants enter the food chain, as a result of climate change-related changes in water sources. This is especially important for irrigation-intensive crops, which need a lot of water to grow.

- Pathogens related to temperature, given that warmer temperatures have the potential to accelerate the growth of foodborne pathogens such as *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella*. This poses a serious risk, especially with fresh and minimally processed products, like fruits and vegetables.

- Transmission of foodborne illnesses, assuming that as a result of climate change, pathogens may spread to new geographic areas, increasing the risk of new and unusual foodborne illness cases.

- Shifts in food distribution patterns because changes in agricultural and supply networks may bring new hazards that could compromise food safety, particularly during storage and transportation.

Strategies for adaptation and mitigation

- Integrated pest management (IPM) where chemical residues can be reduced by using sustainable pest management methods. Pheromone traps and biological control agents may be used on the crops.

- Climate-resilient crops by creating pest- and weather-resistant varieties can help sustain yield and lessen the need for chemical treatments.

- Enhanced water management to avoid microbiological contamination, especially during the irrigation and processing stages, it is essential to ensure water quality through efficient management and treatment.

In summary, food safety has become more complex as a result of climate change, requiring a proactive, multifaceted approach. This covers ongoing studies, creating policies, and putting new technology into practice. In order to respond to the changing problems brought about by climate change and maintain a safe and secure global food supply, cooperation across sectors and borders is essential.

Conclusion

This review emphasizes climate change's broad and multidimensional effects on agriculture, food security, and human health. While there may be some short-term benefits, such as CO₂ fertilization and longer growing seasons, these are far outweighed by the challenges of increased pest infestations, water scarcity, soil degradation, and increased risks of food safety issues like pesticide residues and mycotoxin contamination. The emergence of vector-borne diseases demonstrates the complex interaction between climate change and public health threats. This analysis stresses how crucial it is to develop coordinated adaptation and mitigation measures to address these difficulties. In the face of a rapidly changing environment, it is clearly the time for intensified research, interdisciplinary collaboration, and proactive legislative measures to maintain sustainable agricultural practices, food security, and public health.

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